

Title: ***Escherichia coli* BL21-AI growth and lysis
procedure for HiBiT-tagged intracellular protein production**

Document ID: **SOPGD-094 (version 2)**

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Type of change	External document for Customer
Description of Changes	Update procedures that were added during rerun of the experiment
Reason for Changes	Update protocol version shared in final report for Customer

1. Purpose

Procedure for culturing and lysis of *Escherichia coli* BL21-AI strains for HiBiT-tagged protein production in 96-well plate format. This culture protocol utilizes walkup automation.

2. Scope

- 2.1. **Applicable teams:** This procedure was developed for use in high throughput screening, but may be used for smaller-scale development work.
- 2.2. **Biological scope or principle:** Protein production is induced by the addition of IPTG and L-arabinose in the production phase
- 2.3. **Associated assays:** This culturing procedure was developed for quantitation of intracellular HiBiT-tagged protein concentration using the HiBiT plate assay referenced in Section 7.
- 2.4. **Automation:** This procedure utilizes walk-up automation.

3. Safety Information

3.1. Environmental Health and Safety (EHS) Protocols

3.1.1. All waste can be disposed of as non-hazardous cell waste.

3.2. Safety Data Sheet (SDS) References

3.2.1. N/A

3.3. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and Proper Lab Attire

3.3.1. Lab coat, safety glasses and gloves are required for all BSL1 & BSL2 labs.

3.3.2. Long hair must be tied and no skin exposed.

3.3.3. Footwear must be closed toe shoes

3.4. Special Safety Requirements

3.4.1. None

4. Material requirements

Software & Equipment		
Name / Equipment Type	Vendor	Model #, Version, etc.
Hamilton 96-head	Hamilton	Model name: STAR (96)
STARplus Microplate	Agilent	Model number: G5581A
barcode labeler		

Combi Multidrop	Thermo Scientific	Catalog number: 5840300
Standard tube dispensing cassette	Thermo Scientific	Catalog number: 24072670
3 mm plate shaker w/ humidity control	Infors USA	Model number: I10103.1P
Platoloc thermal microplate sealer	Agilent	Model number: G5585BA
Synergy Neo2 microplate reader	Biotek	Model name: Neo2SM

Benchtop rotor centrifuge	Fisher Scientific	Model number: 75004521
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Chemicals & Reagents				
Name	Vendor	CAS / Catalog #	Storage Conditions	Storage Location
TB media	Ginkgo media team	Custom order	Room temperature	Bench of laboratory personnel
20% L-arabinose	Teknova	G2010	Room temperature	Bench of laboratory personnel
Reverse Osmosis Deionized Water	Boston BioProducts	C-WT-040	Room temperature	Media stock shelves
50 mg/mL Kanamycin	Boston BioProducts	C-ABT-305	4°C	4°C refrigerator shelf of laboratory personnel
IPTG	Sigma	367-93-1	-20°C	-20°C freezer shelf of laboratory personnel
BugBuster Protein Extraction Reagent	Millipore	70584	Room temperature	Bench of laboratory personnel
Benzonase	Millipore	70746-3	-20°C	-20°C freezer

Nuclease (10kU)				shelf of laboratory personnel
cComplete Protease Inhibitor cocktail (EDTA free)	Roche	11873580001	4°C	4°C refrigerator shelf of laboratory personnel

rLysozyme (6000kU)	Millipore	71110-5	-20°C	-20°C freezer shelf of laboratory personnel
1 M DTT	Teknova	D0060	-20°C	-20°C freezer shelf of laboratory personnel

Consumables				
Name	Vendor	Catalog #	Storage Conditions	Storage Location
96-well 2mL v-bottom plate	Eppendorf	951033502	Room temperature	Consumables shelves
96-well clear flat-bottom plate	Corning	9017	Room temperature	Consumables shelves
384-well Echo PP Plus plate	Labcyte	PPL-0200	Room temperature	Consumables shelves
96-well 1.1mL round-bottom plate	Axygen	P-DW-11-C-S	Room temperature	Consumables shelves
50 µL nested clear sterile tips, 96	Hamilton	235964	Room temperature	Consumables shelves
300 µL nested clear sterile tips, 96	Hamilton	235965	Room temperature	Consumables shelves

Aeraseals Andwin Scientific BS25 Room Consumables shelves
temperature

5. Input Sample Requirements

5.1. Incoming Sample Requirements/Data Acceptance Criteria

5.1.1. **Sample composition:** Input samples must be stocked in LB or TB media containing 20-30% glycerol

5.1.2. **Sample volume:** Input samples must contain 50-70 µL/well

5.1.3. **Sample format:** Input samples must be arrayed in 384-well Echo PP (Plus)

plates (Labcyte PPL-0200 or Labcyte PP-0200). Plates must be barcoded on the south and east sides of the plate.

5.1.4. *Note: If procedure is used for a screen, strains must be arrayed according to HTS plate layout version 1 (referenced in Section 7), with process control strains present in all input plates.*

5.2. Unacceptable Samples / Data

5.2.1. Samples with insufficient volume or in a plate type other than Echo (Labcyte PPL-0200 or Labcyte PP-0200) will not be accepted.

5.3. Incoming Sample Storage

5.3.1. Samples will be stored at -80°C prior to execution of this workflow.

6. Process Aids

6.1. Culture procedure:

6.2. Lysis procedure:

6.3. Culture plate layout:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
A	Green											Yellow	
B	Yellow											Green	
C	Green											Yellow	
D	Yellow											Green	
E	Green											Yellow	
F	Blue											Green	
G	Green											Blue	
H	Yellow											Green	
	Green	Positive control					8						
	Blue	Negative control					2						
	Yellow	Media blank					6						
	Grey	Library					80						

6.4. Lysate plate layout:

9.1.2. Centrifuge glycerol sample plates at 500 rpm for 15 seconds, at start. 9.1.2.1.

Note: Centrifuging plates prior to the start of the procedure spins down any droplets on the top of the plate seals to prevent cross-contamination.

9.1.3. Prepare preculture media in a sterile bottle, scaling amounts to the desired volume (each culture plate requires 60 mL of media); Per 1L of media:

Media component	Volume (mL), per 1L
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TB media 1000 mL

50 mg/mL Kanamycin 1 mL

9.1.4. Barcode 96-well deepwell preculture plates using the V-code

9.1.5. Set up the Multidrop Combi to dispense preculture media with a standard size cassette

9.1.5.1. See [SOPGEN-108](#)

9.1.5.2. *Note: A Combi cassette specific to TB media with Kanamycin should be used to dispense media.*

9.1.6. Fill preculture plates with 500 μ L/well of preculture media on the Combi, using the following settings:

Parameter	Value
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Plate type	96 DWP (44 mm)
Dispensing cassette and volume	500 μ L Standard cassette
Column selection	Full plate
Protocol	Default protocol

9.1.7. Stamp 5 μ L/well of glycerol samples into preculture plates on a Hamilton 96-head STAR, using the following USP settings:

USP parameter	Value
operation _type	plate_stamping

tip_choice_input_ul	50_nested
tips_change	yes
lld_aspirate	no
aspirate_height_mm	1
lld_dispense	no
dispense_height_mm	2
mix_cycles_aspirate	3
mix_vol_apsirate_ul	25

mix_cycles_dispense 3

mix_vol_dispense_ul 50

liquid_class water

optimization destination

9.1.8. Seal preculture plates with breathable Aeraseal

9.1.9. Incubate preculture plates in an Infors at the following set-points for 18-22 hours:

Parameter	Setpoint
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Temperature 37°C

Shake speed	1000 rpm
Humidity	80%

9.2. Day 2: Preculture to Production

9.2.1. Prepare production media in a sterile bottle, scaling amounts to the desired volume (each culture plate requires 60 mL of media); Per 1L of media:

Media component	Volume (mL), per 1L
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TB media	1000 mL
50 mg/mL Kanamycin	1 mL

9.2.2. Barcode 96-well deepwell production plates using the V-code 9.2.3. Set up the Multidrop Combi to dispense preculture media with a standard size cassette

9.2.3.1. See [SOPGEN-108](#)

9.2.3.2. *Note: A Combi cassette specific to TB media with Kanamycin should be used to dispense media.*

9.2.4. Fill production plates with 500 µL/well of production media on the Combi, using the following settings:

Parameter	Value
Plate type	96 DWP (44 mm)
Dispensing cassette and volume	500µL Standard cassette
Column selection	Full plate
Protocol	Default protocol

9.2.5. Remove culture plates from the Infors and remove seals manually, then stamp 10 µL/well of preculture samples into production plates on a Hamilton 96-head STAR, using the following USP settings:

USP parameter	Value
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operation _type plate_stamping

tip_choice_input_ul 50_nested

tips_change	yes
lld_aspirate	no
aspirate_height_mm	4
lld_dispense	no
dispense_height_mm	2
mix_cycles_aspirate	5

mix_vol_apsirate_ul	50
mix_cycles_dispense	5
mix_vol_dispense_ul	50
liquid_class	water
optimization	destination

9.2.6. Seal production plates with breathable Aeraseal

9.2.7. Incubate preculture plates in an Infors at the following set-points for 2 hours:

Parameter	Setpoint
Temperature	37°C
Shake speed	1000 rpm
Humidity	80%

9.3. Day 2: Induction

9.3.1. Prepare inducer solution in a sterile bottle, scaling amounts to the desired volume (each culture plate requires 2 mL); Per 100 mL:

Media component	Volume (mL), per 100 mL
1M IPTG	2.5 mL
20% arabinose	50 mL
Water	47.5 mL

9.3.2. Remove culture plates from the Infors and remove seals manually, then dispense 10 µL/well inducer solution into production plates on the Combi, using the following settings:

Parameter	Value
Plate type	96 DWP (44 mm)
Dispensing cassette and volume	10µL Standard cassette

Column selection	Full plate
Protocol	Default protocol

9.3.3. Seal production plates with breathable Aeraseal

9.3.4. Incubate preculture plates in an Infors at the following set-points for 18-22 hours:

Parameter	Setpoint
Temperature	25°C
Shake speed	1000 rpm
Humidity	80%

9.4. Day 3: Production Harvest

9.4.1. Barcode 96-well clear flat-bottom OD plates using the V-code. 9.4.2. Set up the Multidrop Combi to dispense PBS with a standard size cassette. 9.4.2.1. See [SOPGEN-108](#)

9.4.2.2. Note: A Combi cassette specific to PBS should be used to dispense media.

9.4.3. Fill OD plates with 190 µL/well of PBS on the Combi, using the following settings:

Parameter	Value
Plate type	96 standard (15 mm)
Dispensing cassette and volume	190µL Standard cassette
Column selection	Full plate
Protocol	Default protocol

9.4.4. Barcode 96-well halfdeep pellet plates using the V-code 9.4.5. Remove production plates from the Infors and remove seals manually. 9.4.6. Stamp 10 µL/well of production samples into OD plates on a Hamilton 96-head STAR, using the following USP settings:

USP parameter	Value
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operation_type	plate_stamping
tip_choice_input_ul	50_nested
tips_change	yes
lld_aspirate	no
aspirate_height_mm	4
lld_dispense	no
dispense_height_mm	2
mix_cycles_aspirate	5
mix_vol_aspirate_ul	50
mix_cycles_dispense	5
mix_vol_dispense_ul	50
liquid_class	water
optimization	destination

9.4.7. Measure absorbance and fluorescence on a Biotek plate reader:

Parameter	Setting
Plate type	96 well plate
Absorbance wavelength	600 nm
Fluorescence 1 excitation wavelength	587 nm
Fluorescence 1 emission wavelength	610 nm
Fluorescence 1 gain	90
Fluorescence 2 excitation wavelength	479 nm

Fluorescence 2 emission wavelength	520 nm
Fluorescence 2 gain	55

9.4.8. Stamp 250 μ L/well of production samples into pellet plates on a Hamilton 96-head STAR, using the following USP settings:

USP parameter	Value
operation _type	plate_stamping
tip_choice_input_ul	300_nested
tips_change	yes
lld_aspirate	no
aspirate_height_mm	2
lld_dispense	no
dispense_height_mm	2
mix_cycles_aspirate	5
mix_vol_apsirate_ul	250
mix_cycles_dispense	0
mix_vol_dispense_ul	0
liquid_class	water
optimization	destination

9.4.9. Seal pellet plates with a foil seal using a Plateloc.

9.4.10. Centrifuge pellet plates at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes, at speed. 9.4.11.

Remove seals and carefully decant supernatant from pelleted cultures 9.4.12.

Store cell pellets at -80°C prior to lysis.

9.5. Day 4: Lysis:

9.5.1. Thaw frozen pellet plates at room temperature.

9.5.1.1. *Note: Pellet plates may also be thawed in a 30°C Infors (shaking not required)*

9.5.2. Prepare lysis buffer in a sterile bottle, scaling amounts to the desired volume (each lysis plate requires 30 mL of buffer); Per 100 mL of buffer:

Buffer component	Volume, per 100 mL
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1X BugBuster	100 mL
2.5 units/mL Benzonase Nuclease	10 µL
3000 units/mL rLysozyme	10 µL
1M DTT	100 µL
cOmplete Protease inhibitor	2 tablets

9.5.3. Set up the Multidrop Combi to dispense lysis buffer with a standard size cassette

9.5.3.1. See [SOPGEN-108](#)

9.5.3.2. *Note: A Combi cassette specific to BugBuster chemical lysis buffer should be used to dispense media.*

9.5.4. Fill pellet plates with 250 µL/well of lysis buffer on the Combi, using the following settings:

Parameter	Value
Plate type	96 DWP low (22 mm)* <i>*adjust height to 29 mm</i>
Dispensing cassette and volume	250µL Standard cassette
Column selection	Full plate
Protocol	Default protocol

9.5.5. Seal pellet plates with a foil seal using a Plateloc.

9.5.6. Incubate in an Infors at the following set-points for 30 minutes.

Parameter	Setpoint
Temperature	25°C
Shake speed	1000 rpm
Humidity	80%

9.5.7. Centrifuge lysis sample plates at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes, at speed.

9.5.8. Barcode 96-well clear flat-bottom 10X, 100X and 1000X dilution plates using the V-code.

9.5.9. Set up the Multidrop Combi to dispense PBS with a standard size cassette.

9.5.9.1. See [SOPGEN-108](#)

9.5.9.2. Note: A Combi cassette specific to PBS should be used to dispense media.

9.5.10. Fill dilution plates with 180 μ L/well of PBS on the Combi, using the following settings:

Parameter	Value
Plate type	96 standard (15 mm)
Dispensing cassette and volume	190 μ L Standard cassette
Column selection	Full plate
Protocol	Default protocol

9.5.11. Remove clarified lysis sample plates from the centrifuge 9.5.12. Stamp 20 μ L/well of clarified lysis samples into 10X dilution plates on a Hamilton 96-head STAR, using the following USP settings:

USP parameter	Value
operation_type	plate_stamping
tip_choice_input_ul	300_nested
tips_change	yes
lld_aspirate	no
aspirate_height_mm	4
lld_dispense	no
dispense_height_mm	2
mix_cycles_aspirate	0

mix_vol_aspirate_ul 0

mix_cycles_dispense 5

mix_vol_dispense_ul	100
liquid_class	water

optimization	destination
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9.5.13. Measure fluorescence of 10X dilution plates on a Biotek plate reader:

Parameter	Setting
Plate type	96 well plate
Fluorescence 1 excitation wavelength	587 nm
Fluorescence 1 emission wavelength	610 nm
Fluorescence 1 gain	80
Fluorescence 2 excitation wavelength	479 nm
Fluorescence 2 emission wavelength	520 nm
Fluorescence 2 gain	50
Fluorescence 3 excitation wavelength	569 nm

Fluorescence 3 emission wavelength 594 nm

Fluorescence 3 gain 55

9.5.14. Stamp 20 μ L/well of 10X dilution samples into 100X dilution plates on a Hamilton 96-head STAR, using the following USP settings:

USP parameter	Value
operation_type	plate_stamping
tip_choice_input_ul	300_nested
tips_change	yes
lld_aspirate	no
aspirate_height_mm	2
lld_dispense	no

dispense_height_mm 2

mix_cycles_aspirate	5
mix_vol_aspirate_ul	100
mix_cycles_dispense	5
mix_vol_dispense_ul	100
liquid_class	water
optimization	destination

9.5.15. Measure fluorescence of 100X dilution plates on a Biotek plate reader:

Parameter	Setting
Plate type	96 well plate
Fluorescence 1 excitation wavelength	587 nm
Fluorescence 1 emission wavelength	610 nm
Fluorescence 1 gain	80
Fluorescence 2 excitation wavelength	479 nm
Fluorescence 2 emission wavelength	520 nm
Fluorescence 2 gain	50
Fluorescence 3 excitation wavelength	569 nm
Fluorescence 3 emission wavelength	594 nm
Fluorescence 3 gain	55

9.5.16. Stamp 20 μ L/well of 100X dilution samples into 1000X dilution plates on a Hamilton 96-head STAR, using the following USP settings:

USP parameter	Value
operation_type	plate_stamping
tip_choice_input_ul	300_nested
tips_change	yes

lld_aspirate	no
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aspirate_height_mm	2
lld_dispense	no
dispense_height_mm	2
mix_cycles_aspirate	5
mix_vol_aspirate_ul	100
mix_cycles_dispense	5
mix_vol_dispense_ul	100
liquid_class	water
optimization	destination

9.5.17. Measure fluorescence of 1000X dilution plates on a Biotek plate reader:

Parameter	Setting
Plate type	96 well plate
Fluorescence 1 excitation wavelength	587 nm
Fluorescence 1 emission wavelength	610 nm
Fluorescence 1 gain	80
Fluorescence 2 excitation wavelength	479 nm
Fluorescence 2 emission wavelength	520 nm
Fluorescence 2 gain	50
Fluorescence 3 excitation wavelength	569 nm
Fluorescence 3 emission wavelength	594 nm
Fluorescence 3 gain	55

9.5.18. Barcode 384-well Echo PP Plus consolidated lysate plates using the V-code

9.5.19. Stamp 50 μ L/well of clarified lysate and diluted lysate samples from lysis plates, 10X dilution plates, 100X dilution plates and 1000X dilution plates into consolidated lysate plates on a Hamilton 96-head STAR, using the following USP settings:

USP parameter	Value
operation _type	plate_stamping
tip_choice_input_ul	50_nested
tips_change	yes
lld_aspirate	no
aspirate_height_mm	3
lld_dispense	no
dispense_height_mm	2
mix_cycles_aspirate	0
mix_vol_apsirate_ul	0
mix_cycles_dispense	0

mix_vol_dispense_ul 0

liquid_class water

optimization destination

9.5.20. Seal lysate plates with a foil seal using a Plateloc and store at -80°C.

10. Data Analysis

10.1. **Data analysis requirements:** If using Spotfire and Snowflake Information Links, the following steps should be taken prior to starting data analysis:

10.1.1. LIMS sample contents:

10.1.1.1. All input samples should contain the correct strain ID (tID)

10.1.2. Campaign metadata:

10.1.2.1. All culture samples should be labeled with the **production** intent-label

10.1.2.2. All production culture OD samples should be labeled with the **production** intent-label and **od** substep.

10.1.2.3. All in-plate positive control samples should be labeled with the **positive** assay-control label

10.1.2.4. All in-plate negative control samples should be labeled with the **negative** assay-control label

10.1.2.5. All in-plate media blank control samples should be labeled with the **blank** assay-control label

10.2. Data analysis protocol

10.2.1. **Step 1:** Calculate the optical density of each production sample:

optical density of production culture = [(data_value - background)]*(dilution_factor)

where:

- data_value = raw absorbance value at 600 nm from the platereader
- background = 0.04
- dilution_factor = 20

10.2.2. **Step 2:** Calculate QC metrics

10.2.2.1. Resolution (Z-prime):

Z-prime is calculated within each plate based on the measured value of optical density of production culture for positive and media blank samples:

$$Z\text{-prime} = 1 - [3 * (SD_{\text{positive}} + SD_{\text{blank}}) / (\text{mean}_{\text{positive}} - \text{mean}_{\text{blank}})]$$

where:

- SD_positive = standard deviation of optical density of production culture for positive control samples
- SD_blank = standard deviation of optical density of production culture media blank samples
- mean_positive = mean of optical density of production culture for positive control samples
- mean_blank = mean of optical density of production culture for media blank samples

10.2.2.2. Measurement repeatability (CV%):

CV% is calculated within each plate based on the optical density of production culture value for the positive control samples:

$$CV\% = (SD_positive / mean_positive) * 100$$

10.3. Data return summary:

10.3.1. Per **assay** sample quantities:

10.3.1.1. Optical density of production culture (AU)

10.3.2. Per **culture container**:

10.3.2.1. cv% (of the in-plate positive control samples)

10.3.2.2. Z-prime (based on the in-plate positive control and media blank samples)

10.4. QC metrics (Acceptance criteria):

The following metrics are used to determine whether data is designated as 'qc-pass' or 'qc-fail'

QC metric	Measure	Suggested Cutoff value	Influences qc-decision?
Measurement repeatability	cv%	≤30%	No
Resolution	z-prime	> 0	Yes

10.5. Measurement issues:

The following criteria/cutoffs are used to determine hts-measure-issue values

hts-measure-issue	How it is used in this assay
instrument-error	Applied to samples or containers affected by a known instrument issue
human-error	Applied to samples or containers affected by a known human error
no-issues	no identified problems with the sample

10.6. Rework Protocol

10.6.1. Containers that do not pass QC will be re-assayed.